

Cadmium(II) Perchlorate Complexes with Group VB Donor Ligands

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Tertiary phosphine complexes of zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) halides were first reported in 1940¹. Since then, the phosphine complexes of several other mercury(II) derivatives such as pseudohalides, carboxylates, nitrate and perchlorate have been characterised²⁻⁴. For cadmium(II) however, phosphine complexes of only halide derivatives have been studied in detail⁵. A brief report on triphenylphosphine complexes with cadmium(II) salts of oxyanions has also appeared⁶.

In this communication preparation and characterisation of cadmium(II) perchlorate (1) complexes with several tertiary phosphines, triphenylantimony and 2,6-dimethylpyridine are described. Triphenylphosphine oxide complex has been included for comparison.

Results and Discussion

Unlike mercury(II) perchlorate which forms both 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with tertiary phosphines and arsines^{9,10}, cadmium(II) perchlorate (1) gives only 1:2 complexes with tertiary phosphines. Attempts to prepare 1:1 complexes afforded 1:2 complexes and unreacted 1. In this respect 1 resembles cadmium(II) halides.

All the complexes (Tables 1 and 2) are white crystalline solid, soluble in dichloromethane, chloroform and acetone, but insoluble in non-polar solvents. Molar conductance values of the tertiary phosphine complexes ($10^{-3}M$ in dichloromethane) were $10-15 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ showing slight, if

any, ionisation of these complexes in solution (the molar conductance for the 1:1 electrolyte NEt_4ClO_4 , in dichloromethane has been found to be $40 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$). The ΔM values in acetone indicate that the complex $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{DP}$ behaves as a 1:1 electrolyte, whereas all other complexes behave as 1:2 electrolyte⁷.

The infrared frequencies due to the perchlorate groups for all the complexes were assigned with reasonable certainty by comparing the spectra with that of the free phosphines. The ir spectra of $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{PR}_3$ show splitting of ν_3 and ν_4 bands into two appearing at $\sim (1125, 1180)$ and $\sim (630, 620 \text{ cm}^{-1})$ respectively, indicating the presence of monodentately bonded perchlorate groups⁸. A medium absorption at $930-920 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ν_1 which has become infrared active (due to reduction of the local symmetry of ClO_4 from T_d to C_{3v}) is also consistent with the presence of covalently bonded perchlorate groups. The non-electrolytic nature of these complexes in dichloromethane further supports this observation. The analogous mercury(II) complexes, $\text{Hg}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{PR}_3$ have also been assigned tetrahedral structure with monodentate perchlorate groups². The complex $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{PPh}_3$ was previously assigned an octahedral geometry with bidentate perchlorate groups⁶.

Like tertiary phosphines, triphenylantimony also afforded 1:2 complex with cadmium(II) perchlorate. This is interesting because Ph_3Sb does not form complexes with cadmium(II) halides. It is non-conducting in dichloromethane but behaves as

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p. °C	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.)		Molar cond.	
		C	H	Acetone $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	Dichloromethane mol^{-1}
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{PPh}_3$	190	51.6 (51.7)	3.7 (3.6)	180	14.0
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2(p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{P}$	135	53.9 (54.8)	4.5 (4.5)	172	13.2
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2(o\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{P}$	108	54.8 (54.8)	4.5 (4.5)	167.8	14.8
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2(p\text{-CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{P}$	158	48.9 (49.6)	4.1 (4.1)	170	15.01
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot (\text{DP})$	180	46.5 (45.9)	3.1 (3.1)	158	14.8
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}$	210d	31.0 (31.1)	3.4 (3.4)	169	15.2
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb}$	198	41.8 (42.4)	2.6 (2.9)	168	12.80
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{Ph}_3\text{PO}$	190d	60.3 (60.7)	4.2 (4.2)	320	12.6

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm^{-1})

Compd.	Perchlorate		Pure ligand	Complex
	ν_3	ν_4		
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{PPh}_3$	1 125, 1 080	630, 620	VC-P 1 089	VC-P 1 105
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2(p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{P}$	1 130, 1 080	630, 622		
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2(o\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{P}$	1 125, 1 080	630, 620		
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2(p\text{-CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{P}$	1 130, 1 090	630, 616		
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot (\text{DP})$	1 122, 1 082	630, 620		
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}$	1 120, 1 080	630, 622	VC-N 1 568	VC-N 1 630
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb}$	1 135, 1 090	630, 618	VC-Sb 450	VC-Sb 435
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{Ph}_3\text{PO}$	1 115, 1 080	628, 620	VP-O 1 195	VP-O 1 185

1:2 electrolyte in acetone. The ir spectrum (Table 2) of $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{SbPh}_3$, is consistent with a tetrahedral environment around cadmium with two monodentate perchlorate groups. Triphenyl phosphine, however, displaces both the Ph_3Sb molecules from $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{SbPh}_3$ to give $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{PPh}_3$. This is not surprising as Ph_3P is a stronger Lewis base than Ph_3Sb . Triphenylarsine and triphenylbismuth were recovered unchanged after being heated (5 h) with $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ in refluxing dichloromethane. While the latter is well known to be a weak Lewis base, the former case is surprising and we are, at present, unable to explain this observation. Ph_3PO gives a colourless 1 : 4 complex with cadmium(II) perchlorate, which behaves as non-electrolyte in dichloromethane. This suggests that the perchlorate groups in $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{Ph}_3\text{PO}$

are also coordinated to cadmium. Appearance of ν_3 at 1 115 and 1 080 cm^{-1} and ν_4 at 628 and 620 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{Ph}_3\text{PO}$ is consistent with the presence of monodentately bonded perchlorate groups giving rise to an octahedral geometry around cadmium. Coordination through the oxygen atom of triphenylphosphine oxide is inferred by the negative shift of $\nu_{\text{P=O}}$ ⁹.

2,6-Dimethylpyridine ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}$) also gave 1 : 2 complex with cadmium(II) perchlorate. Its non-conducting behaviour in dichloromethane and splitting of ν_3 and ν_4 modes into two peaks each, suggest a tetrahedral geometry around cadmium. Coordination from the N atom of the base is indicated by the positive shift of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of the pyridine¹⁰.

Attempts to increase the coordination number of cadmium by reacting Ph_3P with $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$ ($\text{L} = \text{NC}_7\text{H}_9$ or Ph_3P) failed; even the pyridine was not displaced by Ph_3P . Thus, the Lewis basicity of ligands towards $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ appears to decrease in the order : $\text{NC}_7\text{H}_9 \geq \text{Ph}_3\text{P} > \text{Ph}_3\text{Sb} > \text{Ph}_3\text{Bi}$

Experimental

The solid Lewis bases (Aldrich) were used as such. Solvents were dried by conventional methods. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer.

Preparation of the complexes : Two typical experiments are given here. (i) Silver perchlorate (0.204 g, 0.98 mmol) was added to a solution of cadmium(II) iodide (0.18 g, 0.49 mmol) in dichloromethane (20 ml) containing acetone (5 ml). After stirring the mixture at room temperature for ~ 2 h the silver iodide was filtered off. The filtrate was then treated with a solution of tri-*p*-tolylphosphine (0.3 g, 0.98 mmol) in dichloromethane (5 ml). The resulting solution was refluxed for ~ 5 h and then concentrated. Addition of petroleum ether (b.p.40–60°) and cooling afforded colourless crystalline complex, $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{P}(p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_3$. The complexes $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$ [$\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3$, (*p*- $\text{CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4$) $_3\text{P}$, DP, NC_7H_9 and Ph_3Sb] were prepared similarly. (ii) To a solution of $\text{CdI}_2 \cdot 2\text{PPh}_3$ (0.3 g, 0.39 mmol) in dichloromethane (20 ml) was added silver perchlorate (0.16 g, 0.77 mmol). The mixture was refluxed with stirring for ~5 h. The silver iodide was then filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated to give $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{PPh}_3$ in ~ 85% yield. $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2(p\text{-CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{P}$ was also obtained by this method.

A mixture of PPh_3 (0.10 g, 0.61 mmol) and $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{SbPh}_3$ (0.31 g, 0.304 mmol) was stirred in refluxing dichloromethane (15 ml) for ~ 4 h. The solvent was then distilled off and the residue extracted with petroleum ether. Removal of the volatiles under reduced pressure gave SbPh_3

(0.18 g, 60%), m.p. 49° (lit.¹¹ 49.5°). The residue was found to be $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{PPh}_3$ (0.23 g, 74.1%) (authentic ir spectrum).

To a solution of cadmium(II) perchlorate [prepared from cadmium(II) iodide (0.98 g, 0.26 mmol) and silver perchlorate (0.11 g, 0.53 mmol)] in dichloromethane (25 ml) containing acetone (5 ml), was added Ph_3PO (0.3 g, 1.07 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for ~ 6 h. The volatiles were removed under reduced pressure and the residue was crystallised with dichloromethane/petroleum ether to give colourless $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{Ph}_3\text{PO}$.

To a solution of the pyridine complex (0.2 g, 0.38 mmol) in dichloromethane was added triphenylphosphine (0.19 g, 0.75 mmol). After refluxing the mixture for 5 h, the solvent was distilled off. The residue was washed with petroleum ether (3 × 5 ml) and was found to be the unreacted pyridine complex (~ 90%) (authentic ir spectrum). Removal of the petroleum ether under reduced pressure gave unreacted Ph_3P (~ 90%), m.p. 70°.

Under similar conditions, cadmium(II) perchlorate failed to react with Ph_3As (or Ph_3Bi) as did CdBr_2 with Ph_3As (or Ph_3Sb).

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